

Mixed Integer Nonlinear Formulation of the Chargym Environment

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1 Purpose and Scope

This note gives a standalone mixed-integer nonlinear programming (MINLP) formulation for the fixed deep-reinforcement-learning (DRL) actor and the Chargym electric-vehicle charging-station environment used in the verification experiments. The purpose is to make explicit the model on which the exact lower-bound claim rests. The formulation follows the Chargym setting [1]: a station with $n = 10$ charging piles, vehicle-to-grid operation, photovoltaic generation, grid purchase cost, and departure penalties for undercharged vehicles.

Exactness here means exactness for the encoded verification problem. The fixed actor, logical events, charging/discharging limits, arrival and departure events, reward terms, and admissible exogenous uncertainty sets are represented directly in the MINLP. ReLU, max, min, and logical relations are encoded with mixed-integer constraints using valid propagated bounds. The actor's *tanh* output and the binary-gated quadratic departure penalty are kept as native nonlinear expressions handled by the global MINLP solver.

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2 State, Action, and Uncertainty

At verification step k , the normalized Chargym observation is $x_k^{\text{nn}} \in [0, 1]^{28}$ and is ordered as

$$x_k^{\text{nn}} = (\sigma_k, \pi_k, \hat{\sigma}_{k+1}, \hat{\pi}_{k+1}, \hat{\sigma}_{k+2}, \hat{\pi}_{k+2}, \hat{\sigma}_{k+3}, \hat{\pi}_{k+3}, s_{k,1}, \dots, s_{k,n}, T_{k,1}, \dots, T_{k,n})^\top. \quad (1)$$

Here σ_k and π_k are the normalized current solar-radiation and price variables, $(\hat{\sigma}, \hat{\pi})$ are the three look-ahead forecast pairs, $s_{k,i}$ is the state of charge (SoC) of pile i , and $T_{k,i}$ is normalized time to leave (TTL). The physical TTL count is

$$h_{k,i} = HT_{k,i}, \quad h_{k,i} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}, \quad H = 24. \quad (2)$$

The action is $a_k = (a_{k,1}, \dots, a_{k,n})^\top \in [-1, 1]^n$. Positive actions charge a connected EV and negative actions discharge it through V2G.

The exogenous block w_k contains the current and forecast solar-radiation and price variables. Stochastic Chargym inputs are represented in verification by admissible uncertainty intervals. The normalized exogenous forecast window is shifted one step and refreshed at the far end:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{k+1} &= \hat{\sigma}_{k+1} + \epsilon_{k,0}^\sigma, & \pi_{k+1} &= \hat{\pi}_{k+1} + \epsilon_{k,0}^\pi, \\ \hat{\sigma}_{k+2}^+ &= \hat{\sigma}_{k+2} + \epsilon_{k,1}^\sigma, & \hat{\pi}_{k+2}^+ &= \hat{\pi}_{k+2} + \epsilon_{k,1}^\pi, \\ \hat{\sigma}_{k+3}^+ &= \hat{\sigma}_{k+3} + \epsilon_{k,2}^\sigma, & \hat{\pi}_{k+3}^+ &= \hat{\pi}_{k+3} + \epsilon_{k,2}^\pi, \\ \hat{\sigma}_{k+4}^+ &= \bar{\sigma}_{k+4} + \epsilon_{k,3}^\sigma, & \hat{\pi}_{k+4}^+ &= \bar{\pi}_{k+4} + \epsilon_{k,3}^\pi. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Here $(\bar{\sigma}_{k+4}, \bar{\pi}_{k+4})$ is the nominal far-horizon forecast pair available from the data stream. Each disturbance is bounded, $-\Delta_{k,j}^\sigma \leq \epsilon_{k,j}^\sigma \leq \Delta_{k,j}^\sigma$ and $-\Delta_{k,j}^\pi \leq \epsilon_{k,j}^\pi \leq \Delta_{k,j}^\pi$, or equivalently the resulting next exogenous coordinates lie in induced intervals. Physical price and renewable generation are obtained from fixed denormalization/scaling maps

$$p_k = \alpha_\pi \pi_k + \beta_\pi, \quad \rho_k = \alpha_\sigma \sigma_k + \beta_\sigma, \quad (4)$$

with constants taken from the Chargym data normalization and PV model. Thus the optimizer ranges over all admissible exogenous realizations while the reward uses physical price and renewable-generation quantities.

3 Fixed Actor Formulation

The DRL actor is fixed during verification, so all network weights and biases are constants. For the Chargym DDPG actor used in the paper, the input has 28 coordinates, the hidden layers have 400 and 300 ReLU units, and the output has one coordinate for each charging pile. Let $y_k^0 = x_k^{\text{nn}}$. For hidden layers $\ell = 1, \dots, L-1$,

$$y_k^\ell = W^\ell y_k^{\ell-1} + b^\ell, \quad y_k^\ell = \max\{0, q_k^\ell\}. \quad (5)$$

For each hidden neuron j , with valid pre-activation bounds $\underline{q}_j^\ell \leq q_{k,j}^\ell \leq \bar{q}_j^\ell$, the ReLU equality is encoded exactly as

$$\begin{aligned} y_{k,j}^\ell &\geq q_{k,j}^\ell, & y_{k,j}^\ell &\geq 0, \\ y_{k,j}^\ell &\leq q_{k,j}^\ell - \underline{q}_j^\ell (1 - \delta_{k,j}^\ell), & y_{k,j}^\ell &\leq \bar{q}_j^\ell \delta_{k,j}^\ell, \\ \delta_{k,j}^\ell &\in \{0, 1\}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The output layer gives

$$\tilde{a}_k = W^L y_k^{L-1} + b^L, \quad (7)$$

and the bounded action is the actor's *tanh* output:

$$a_{k,i} = \tanh(\tilde{a}_{k,i}), \quad -1 \leq a_{k,i} \leq 1, \quad i = 1, \dots, n. \quad (8)$$

Equivalently, $a_{k,i} = (\exp(\tilde{a}_{k,i}) - \exp(-\tilde{a}_{k,i})) / (\exp(\tilde{a}_{k,i}) + \exp(-\tilde{a}_{k,i}))$. No additional affine scaling is needed because Chargym uses the action space $[-1, 1]^n$.

4 One-Step Environment Formulation

For each pile i , introduce binary variables $\delta_{\text{prs},k,i}$, $\delta_{\text{mode},k,i}$, $\delta_{\text{chg},k,i}$, $\delta_{\text{dis},k,i}$, and $\delta_{\text{arr},k,i}$ for presence, charge/discharge mode, active charging-limit branch, active discharging-limit branch, and arrival. The binary variable $\ell_{k,i}$ is the departure mask. Continuous auxiliaries include $z_{\text{chg},k,i}$, $z_{\text{dis},k,i}$, $z_{\text{lim},k,i}$, and arrival SoC $s_{\text{arr},k,i}$. The refreshed stay duration $d_{\text{stay},k,i}$ is an integer variable.

4.1 Presence and Mode

Presence is tied to the positive integer TTL count:

$$0 \leq h_{k,i} \leq \bar{h}_{k,i}, \quad \delta_{\text{prs},k,i} \leq h_{k,i}, \quad h_{k,i} \leq \bar{h}_{k,i} \delta_{\text{prs},k,i}. \quad (9)$$

Thus $\delta_{\text{prs},k,i} = 1$ exactly when an EV is present. The mode selector is

$$\delta_{\text{mode},k,i} - 1 \leq a_{k,i} \leq \delta_{\text{mode},k,i}. \quad (10)$$

It selects charging for positive actions and discharging for negative actions. When $a_{k,i} = 0$, either branch is admissible and yields the same SoC update.

4.2 Charging and Discharging Limits

Let C_i be the EV battery capacity and C_i^{pile} the pile power limit. The physical charging and discharging limits are

$$z_{\text{chg},k,i} = \min\{C_i^{\text{pile}}, C_i(1 - s_{k,i})\}, \quad z_{\text{dis},k,i} = \min\{C_i^{\text{pile}}, C_i s_{k,i}\}. \quad (11)$$

Given propagated SoC bounds $\underline{s}_{k,i} \leq s_{k,i} \leq \bar{s}_{k,i}$, these minima are encoded by

$$\begin{aligned} z_{\text{chg},k,i} &\leq C_i^{\text{pile}}, \\ z_{\text{chg},k,i} &\leq C_i(1 - s_{k,i}), \\ z_{\text{chg},k,i} &\geq C_i^{\text{pile}} - \left[C_i^{\text{pile}} - C_i(1 - \bar{s}_{k,i}) \right]_+ \delta_{\text{chg},k,i}, \\ z_{\text{chg},k,i} &\geq C_i(1 - s_{k,i}) - \left[C_i(1 - \underline{s}_{k,i}) - C_i^{\text{pile}} \right]_+ (1 - \delta_{\text{chg},k,i}), \\ z_{\text{dis},k,i} &\leq C_i^{\text{pile}}, \\ z_{\text{dis},k,i} &\leq C_i s_{k,i}, \\ z_{\text{dis},k,i} &\geq C_i^{\text{pile}} - \left[C_i^{\text{pile}} - C_i \underline{s}_{k,i} \right]_+ \delta_{\text{dis},k,i}, \\ z_{\text{dis},k,i} &\geq C_i s_{k,i} - \left[C_i \bar{s}_{k,i} - C_i^{\text{pile}} \right]_+ (1 - \delta_{\text{dis},k,i}). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Define propagated bounds

$$\begin{aligned} z_{\text{chg},k,i} &= \min\{C_i^{\text{pile}}, C_i(1 - \bar{s}_{k,i})\}, & \bar{z}_{\text{chg},k,i} &= \min\{C_i^{\text{pile}}, C_i(1 - \underline{s}_{k,i})\}, \\ z_{\text{dis},k,i} &= \min\{C_i^{\text{pile}}, C_i \underline{s}_{k,i}\}, & \bar{z}_{\text{dis},k,i} &= \min\{C_i^{\text{pile}}, C_i \bar{s}_{k,i}\}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The selected physical limit is $z_{\text{lim},k,i} = z_{\text{chg},k,i}$ in charging mode and $z_{\text{lim},k,i} = z_{\text{dis},k,i}$ in discharging mode:

$$\begin{aligned} z_{\text{lim},k,i} &\leq z_{\text{chg},k,i} + [\bar{z}_{\text{dis},k,i} - \underline{z}_{\text{chg},k,i}]_+ (1 - \delta_{\text{mode},k,i}), \\ z_{\text{lim},k,i} &\geq z_{\text{chg},k,i} - [\bar{z}_{\text{chg},k,i} - \underline{z}_{\text{dis},k,i}]_+ (1 - \delta_{\text{mode},k,i}), \\ z_{\text{lim},k,i} &\leq z_{\text{dis},k,i} + [\bar{z}_{\text{chg},k,i} - \underline{z}_{\text{dis},k,i}]_+ \delta_{\text{mode},k,i}, \\ z_{\text{lim},k,i} &\geq z_{\text{dis},k,i} - [\bar{z}_{\text{dis},k,i} - \underline{z}_{\text{chg},k,i}]_+ \delta_{\text{mode},k,i}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The constants above are valid local constants implied by the propagated bounds for the current abstract element.

4.3 Arrival, SoC, and TTL Updates

Arrivals are allowed only when a pile is empty:

$$\delta_{\text{arr},k,i} \leq 1 - \delta_{\text{prs},k,i}, \quad \delta_{\text{arr},k,i} \in \{0, 1\}. \quad (15)$$

If an arrival occurs, its initial SoC and stay duration satisfy

$$\underline{s}_{\text{arr},k,i} \leq s_{\text{arr},k,i} \leq \bar{s}_{\text{arr},k,i}, \quad d_{\text{stay},k,i} \in \mathcal{D}_{k,i}^{\text{stay}} \subset \mathbb{Z}_{>0}. \quad (16)$$

When $\mathcal{D}_{k,i}^{\text{stay}}$ is a contiguous range, membership is the integer bound $\underline{d}_{k,i}^{\text{stay}} \leq d_{\text{stay},k,i} \leq \bar{d}_{k,i}^{\text{stay}}$. For a non-contiguous admissible set $\mathcal{D}_{k,i}^{\text{stay}} = \{d_1, \dots, d_m\}$, use binary selectors

$$d_{\text{stay},k,i} = \sum_{q=1}^m d_q \eta_{k,i,q}, \quad \sum_{q=1}^m \eta_{k,i,q} = 1, \quad \eta_{k,i,q} \in \{0, 1\}. \quad (17)$$

The admissible arrival law is represented by branch-specific sets: $\delta_{\text{arr},k,i}$ may be fixed to 0 or 1 when the arrival schedule is known, or left free subject to the above arrival-SoC and stay-duration sets when the verification problem ranges over all admissible arrivals in the current abstract element.

For an occupied pile, the next SoC follows the physical charge/discharge law even when the vehicle's TTL count reaches zero after the step. For an already empty pile, the next SoC is either initialized by a new arrival or set to zero:

$$s_{k+1,i} = \delta_{\text{prs},k,i} \left(s_{k,i} + \frac{a_{k,i} z_{\text{lim},k,i}}{C_i} \right) + (1 - \delta_{\text{prs},k,i}) \delta_{\text{arr},k,i} s_{\text{arr},k,i}. \quad (18)$$

The normalized TTL transition is

$$T_{k+1,i} = T_{k,i} - \frac{\delta_{\text{prs},k,i}}{H} + (1 - \delta_{\text{prs},k,i}) \delta_{\text{arr},k,i} \frac{d_{\text{stay},k,i}}{H}. \quad (19)$$

Equivalently, in integer TTL counts,

$$h_{k+1,i} = h_{k,i} - \delta_{\text{prs},k,i} + (1 - \delta_{\text{prs},k,i}) \delta_{\text{arr},k,i} d_{\text{stay},k,i}. \quad (20)$$

5 TTL Event Branches

The formulation preserves integer TTL values. For implementation, each pile and time step can be split into mutually exclusive event regimes, fixing event indicators on each branch:

- Empty/no arrival: $h_{k,i} = 0$, $\delta_{\text{prs},k,i} = 0$, $\delta_{\text{arr},k,i} = 0$, and $h_{k+1,i} = 0$.
- Empty/arrival: $h_{k,i} = 0$, $\delta_{\text{prs},k,i} = 0$, $\delta_{\text{arr},k,i} = 1$, and $h_{k+1,i} = d_{\text{stay},k,i}$ with $d_{\text{stay},k,i} \in \mathcal{D}_{k,i}^{\text{stay}} \subset \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$.
- Occupied/leaving: $h_{k,i} = 1$, $\delta_{\text{prs},k,i} = 1$, departure mask $\ell_{k,i} = 1$, and the countdown gives $h_{k+1,i} = h_{k,i} - 1 = 0$.
- Occupied/staying: $h_{k,i} \geq 2$, $\delta_{\text{prs},k,i} = 1$, $\ell_{k,i} = 0$, and $h_{k+1,i} = h_{k,i} - 1$.

These regimes are exhaustive for $h_{k,i} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ and mutually exclusive after the empty case is split into arrival/no-arrival. Reapplying the same split to descendant branches handles repeated arrivals and departures over the horizon. A departure at step k is the occupied case $h_{k,i} = 1$; applying the same countdown rule as other occupied cases gives $h_{k+1,i} = 0$. Any new arrival at that pile is then considered in the subsequent transition. Because refreshed durations are positive integers and occupied transitions subtract one from an integer TTL, integer-valued TTL trajectories are preserved by induction over time.

6 Reward and Horizon Objective

Chargym uses reward equal to the negative station cost. At step k , the reward is the negative sum of grid-purchase cost and departure penalty:

$$R_k = -(c_k^{\text{grid}} + c_k^{\text{dep}}). \quad (21)$$

The realized pile energy and aggregate station energy are

$$e_{k,i} = a_{k,i} z_{\text{lim},k,i} \delta_{\text{prs},k,i}, \quad E_k = \sum_{i=1}^n e_{k,i}. \quad (22)$$

Here p_k and ρ_k are the physical price and renewable-generation quantities defined from the normalized exogenous state above. Grid purchase has no export revenue:

$$c_k^{\text{grid}} = p_k g_k, \quad g_k = \max\{0, E_k - \rho_k\}. \quad (23)$$

Given valid bounds $\underline{q}_k^{\text{grid}} \leq E_k - \rho_k \leq \bar{q}_k^{\text{grid}}$, the max relation is encoded exactly as

$$\begin{aligned} g_k &\geq E_k - \rho_k, & g_k &\geq 0, \\ g_k &\leq E_k - \rho_k - \underline{q}_k^{\text{grid}}(1 - \delta_k^{\text{grid}}), & g_k &\leq \bar{q}_k^{\text{grid}} \delta_k^{\text{grid}}, \\ \delta_k^{\text{grid}} &\in \{0, 1\}. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The departure penalty is applied when a connected EV leaves after the current step. The mask $\ell_{k,i} = 1$ exactly when $h_{k,i} = 1$. With $0 \leq h_{k,i} \leq \bar{h}_{k,i}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \ell_{k,i} &\in \{0, 1\}, & \ell_{k,i} &\leq \delta_{\text{prs},k,i}, \\ h_{k,i} &\leq 1 + [\bar{h}_{k,i} - 1]_+ (1 - \ell_{k,i}), & h_{k,i} &\geq \ell_{k,i}, \\ h_{k,i} &\geq 2(\delta_{\text{prs},k,i} - \ell_{k,i}). \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

The undercharge amount is

$$u_{k,i} = \max\{0, 1 - s_{k+1,i}\}. \quad (26)$$

For bounds $\underline{q}_{k,i}^{\text{under}} \leq 1 - s_{k+1,i} \leq \bar{q}_{k,i}^{\text{under}}$, impose

$$\begin{aligned} u_{k,i} &\geq 1 - s_{k+1,i}, & u_{k,i} &\geq 0, \\ u_{k,i} &\leq 1 - s_{k+1,i} - \underline{q}_{k,i}^{\text{under}}(1 - \delta_{k,i}^{\text{under}}), & u_{k,i} &\leq \bar{q}_{k,i}^{\text{under}} \delta_{k,i}^{\text{under}}, \\ \delta_{k,i}^{\text{under}} &\in \{0, 1\}. \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

The departure cost is the binary-gated quadratic term

$$c_k^{\text{dep}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \ell_{k,i} (\lambda_{\text{dep}} u_{k,i})^2, \quad \lambda_{\text{dep}} = 2.0. \quad (28)$$

For a look-ahead horizon of length m , the lower-bound verification problem is

$$\min_{\mathbf{v}} - \sum_{k=t}^{t+m-1} \left(c_k^{\text{grid}} + c_k^{\text{dep}} \right) \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{v}) \leq 0. \quad (29)$$

The vector \mathbf{v} collects all policy, environment, uncertainty, event, and reward variables over the horizon. The constraint system $\mathbf{c}(\mathbf{v}) \leq 0$ contains the unrolled fixed-actor equations, exact ReLU and logical encodings, charging/discharging limit constraints, arrival and TTL update rules, admissible uncertainty intervals, and reward definitions above. The optimizer therefore minimizes the return over all trajectories admitted by the encoded fixed policy, Chargym dynamics, integer event logic, and uncertainty sets.

References

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